

THE COLLABORATIVE EXPERIENCE IN LEARNING PROBABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Probability is regarded as one of the branches of Mathematics with many applications and problem-solving situations. It requires critical thinking and problem-solving. The curriculum planners realized its significance, so they included Probability in the curriculum from elementary up to Junior High School in a spiral progression approach and as a core subject in Senior High School. With this, the researcher conducted an experimental study investigating the effectiveness of collaborative learning in teaching Probability. The participants were 66 third year Bachelor of Secondary Education Mathematics students. One group was taught using the traditional lecture-discussion method while the other group was taught using collaborative learning. The experiment was a semester-long study covering 7 chapters. The effectiveness of collaborative learning was measured through a 25-item multiple-choice test. Frequency and Percent, Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-test were used to treat the data gathered. The results showed that the two groups were homogeneous based on their pretest scores. However, after the utilization of collaborative learning, students in the experimental group showed better performance in the posttest than those in the control group. Further, the findings denoted that there is a significant difference between the performance of the experimental and control groups and that the students taught using collaborative learning performed better than those who were taught using the traditional method.

Keywords: *Probability, collaborative learning, pre-service teachers, mathematic, pedagogy, experimental design*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is considered one of the most important subjects in the curriculum. Despite its importance, several students fear Math and struggle in their math subjects for so many reasons. It is, therefore, a mission and a challenge to Mathematics teachers to make their students like Mathematics and later love it.

Various branches of Mathematics need to be learned by students. All of them have various and relevant applications to real-life situations. One of them is Probability, which requires critical thinking and problem-solving. Probability is used in weather forecasting, sports strategies, insurance options, games and recreational activities, risk assessment in business and game theory, environmental regulation, product reliability, defense strategies, medical decision and life expectancy, sale forecasting, scenario analysis, and gambling. It is in this sense that this subject should be understood and mastered by the students for this will greatly help them in the future to whatever endeavor they would pursue. But just like other math subjects, some students find this boring, difficult, not very practical, and abstract (Ignacio et al., 2006), complex, and difficult to understand. Thus, finding ways to effectively teach the subject is of great importance, hence, this study was conducted.

The student's performance in mathematics is always low as compared with other subjects in the curricula. According to the international test called Trends and International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), the performance of Philippine students in the international standardized exams in math is among the lowest in the world (TIMSS, 2003). As of the latest result that the country joined the study, the Philippines ranked 34th out of 38 countries in high school mathematics and ranked last (10th) in Advanced Mathematics (TIMSS, 2008).

With this, the Commission on Higher Education enforced Outcomes-Based Education which aims to uplift the standards of the educational system in the Philippines. Embedded in the curriculum is collaborative learning that would produce not only competitive graduates but could also perform better with the team, especially in the workplace. As stated in CMO 46 series 2012 Article III, Section 11 ... *the changing realities spurred by globalization underscore the shift in contemporary international education discourse from education to lifelong learning, and from education as transmission of expert knowledge to education as building learners' competencies – including learning how to learn*. Further, in Section 12 *Lifelong learning should enable people to develop awareness of themselves and their environment and encourage them to play their social role and work in the community*.

For the students to become lifelong learners the teachers should apply various teaching practices that are well suited to the student's learning ability, integrate mathematical concepts into other disciplines, use appropriate instructional materials and technology, and apply or relate the topics to real-life experiences of the learners (Aplaon, 2015). In addition, preparing them for their social role may be best practiced through a collaborative approach to teaching.

Collaborative learning begins with interaction as described by Henry Ford, it begins with coming together, progressing in keeping together, and ends with success by working together. When students collaborate for learning, they do not just interact, they work together and help one another to achieve a common goal. The contribution of every member to the attainment of the goal and the assistance or help a member receives may vary depending on one's capacities.

Through collaborative learning, students are more likely to succeed because they are exposed to more types of approaches to a concept or a lesson. The use of groups inside and outside the classroom assisted in the students' understanding of the material and gave them additional confidence in their abilities to truly learn math. Working with groups contributes to the improvement of students' attitudes towards mathematics and has a positive effect on students' achievement as it encourages students to be more involved with one another (Curtis, 2009). Effective classroom management of the teachers maximized the students' engagement and motivation. According to Arney (2010), the most successful groups are probably groups of three and are formed by considering their location or interest. Assigning groups with similar backgrounds, abilities, and interests raised the mathematics scores of middle and high school students (Norton, 2009).

The student's performance in mathematics and attitudes towards mathematics were affected by exposure to collaborative learning. Students feel content when sharing knowledge to learn math to function effectively in group work, thus, promoting students' performance in mathematics (Hossain, 2013). Further, working collaboratively enhances understanding and students' self-confidence (Zakaria et al., 2013).

Learning mathematics depends on the presentation, learners' involvement, and learning environment. Teachers' attitude towards teaching mathematics significantly shapes students' attitudes towards learning mathematics (Yara, 2009). Because of this, teachers need to change the practice of teacher-centered teaching methods to student-centered teaching methods. Teachers should select strategies promoting active learning in the classroom. They should also provide the students with opportunities to think for themselves and deliver their solutions to the problems through constant practice, collaborative learning, and other worthwhile tasks (Aplaon, 2017) so that learning becomes an active and creative process (Festus, 2013). Effective Mathematics pedagogy includes acknowledging that all students, irrespective of age, can develop positive mathematical identities and become powerful mathematical learners (Anthony & Walshaw, 2009). Teachers need to master mathematical content to be delivered and plan how to implement collaborative learning better. Just placing the students together in a group does not always result in cooperative learning (Yamarik, 2007). Cooperative learning should be employed so that students can help each other in small groups (Chin et al., 2010).

This study was founded on Lev Vygotsky's (1978) Zone of Proximal Development wherein ZPD is the distance between the actual development level as determined by independent problem-solving and the level of potential development as determined through problem-solving under adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers. He suggests that teachers use collaborative learning exercises where less competent children develop

with help from more skillful peers – with the ZPD because interaction with peers effectively develops skills. He believed that when a student is in the ZPD for a particular task, providing the appropriate assistance will give the student enough of a “boost” to achieve the task. Vygotsky believed that one learns through interactions and communications with others and that learning always occurs and cannot be separated from a social context. The social context may involve student-student and expert-student collaboration on real-world problems or tasks built upon one’s language, skills, and experience shaped by everyone’s culture (Vygotsky, 1962).

Another theory relevant to the study is Slavin’s (1996) Cooperative Learning Theory which posits that the cooperative approach requires the students to cooperate to learn. The students are also responsible for the learning of their group as well as their learning. This method also emphasizes achieving the group’s goals and groups’ success which can be achieved when all group members have learned the intended objectives.

The collaborative learning approach is a currently emerging approach that involves a structured group of learners working together toward a shared goal based on a fixed procedure (Farmer, 1999; Johnson & Johnson, 1985). In collaborative work, students are asked to actively participate, interact, explain, and socialize (Williams, 2007; Johnson et al., 1985). Everyone should take over and use different skills to create a comfortable context to communicate freely and openly with each other (Agarwal & Nandita, 2011). It is an effective instructional technique for a variety of learners in a variety of situations (Slavin, 1995). Collaborative learning encourages students to interact with one another to increase their ability to process information (Slavin, 1996; Johnson et al, 1985) and enhances students’ understanding and confidence in Mathematics (Wong et al., 2016). That way they feel contented when they can function effectively in the group work (Hossain et al, 2013).

The experimental variable is the collaborative learning employed in the Probability class. The said method is chosen by the researcher because the teaching strategies perceived to be most effective by Science and Mathematics teachers at schools identified as benchmarks in teaching and learning practices were hands-on experiences that bring students to their fullest learning capacity. After all, they depend on themselves, cooperative learning because they can share knowledge better when they work in groups rather than when they work alone, and self-discovery because it enhances students’ learning capability (Ulep, 2007).

Numerous studies show a positive effect of cooperative learning methods on Mathematics performance. Ali et al., Hasan (2007), Arasythamby and Chairhany (2012), Keramati (2009), Yu (1998), Melihan and Sirri (2011), and Lee et al., (2018) have shown that there are significant changes between the pretest and posttest in cooperative learning group provided that the students are taught how to work cooperatively together (Yamarik, 2007). Students who learn in a group with cooperative learning are more active (Kagan, 2007), they are in a relaxed learning situation which encourages them to be more forward in asking questions as a group, rather than as an individual (Yamarik, 2007). This makes students active participants in the classroom and allows them to work together as a small family whose sole aim is to make their family succeed (Boudehane, 2015). In cooperative

learning, students can compete and cooperate until they become active and creative in the learning process. As the students increase their interactions with each other, their self-efficacy, participation, understanding, and enjoyment of learning mathematics are promoted (Lee et al., 2018).

In this study, the researcher focused only on collaborative learning because according to Ulep (2007), students are more likely to learn by sharing ideas with small groups and work collaboratively to complete the academic task. Further, Melihan and Sirri (2011) concluded that the cooperative learning method is more effective than the traditional teaching method in the academic success of students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of using collaborative learning in teaching Probability to Third Year Bachelor in Secondary Education Major in mathematics students.

Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of performance in the pre- and post-tests of the students taught using the traditional lecture-discussion method?
2. What is the level of performance in the pre- and post-tests of the students taught using collaborative learning?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest of the control and experimental groups?
4. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the students in the control and experimental groups?
5. Is there a significant difference in the posttest of the two groups?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized an experimental research design wherein the pretest and posttest were utilized. To determine the effectiveness of using collaborative learning in teaching Probability, two groups of students were formed and compared. The first group was taught using the traditional method called the control group and the second group was taught using the collaborative learning method regarded as the experimental group. This is a semester-long study (54 hours) covering seven (7) chapters with topics such as counting techniques, permutations, combinations, probability, distribution of random variables, discrete probability distributions, and continuous probability distributions.

The study was conducted at Mindoro State University (MinSU) Bongabong Campus. Mindoro State University is the only state university on the island of Mindoro which has three campuses located in Victoria, Calapan City Campus, and Bongabong. Mindoro State University Bongabong Campus offers Bachelor of Secondary Education, Bachelor

of Elementary Education, Hospitality Management, Tourism Management, Information Technology, Computer Engineering, and Criminology.

The participants of the study are 66 Third year Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) major in Mathematics students. The researcher utilized stratified random sampling wherein students were categorized as above average, average, and below average based on their average grade in major subjects during the previous semester with grades ranges of 95-100, 88-94, and 80-87, respectively. Each stratum is divided into two for the control and experimental groups. A total of 33 participants per group was formed. The participants in the experimental group were grouped into eight using the same scheme, thus, each group was composed of 4-5 members.

The research instrument used in the study was a comprehensive test comprised of a 25-item multiple-choice test. The Table of Specification was constructed to ensure the proper representation of the different chapters in the instrument. The said instrument was validated by five experts from inside and outside of the institution. It has also undergone a test of reliability using the test-retest method with the aid of Pearson's r with an r -value of 0.882.

Once the instrument was found valid and reliable, the pretest together with the consent forms was distributed to the participants. After the pretest, the two groups were taught using traditional teaching for the control group and collaborative learning for the experimental group. Both groups have the same teacher and use the same materials and textbooks. The only difference is the teaching method. After the conduct of the study, the posttest was given to both groups. One hundred percent of the instrument was retrieved. After the retrieval of the forms, the data gathered were encoded, collated, organized, statistically treated, analyzed, and interpreted.

The scores of the participants in the pretest and posttest were tabulated. Mean, frequency, and percentage were used to determine the performance of the participants in both groups in terms of pretest and posttest. Standard deviation was employed to determine the dispersion of the gathered data, thus, determining the presence of outliers. The t -test, on the other hand, was applied to determine the degree to which the pretest and posttest performances of each group varied; hence, the more effective method was determined.

RESULTS

The result of the study is reported based on the objectives stated earlier as follows:

1. Students' Performance in the Control Group. The independent-sample t -test was conducted by comparing the performance in Probability of the control group. The posttest mean score of students taught using the traditional method was 16.33 (SD = 1.60), and their pretest was 6.02 (SD = 1.23). Table 1 shows that the posttest mean was greater than the pretest mean. The difference between the two tests was significant $t(32) = -$

47.9651, $p < 0.05$ in favor of the posttest, which revealed that the students gained knowledge through the traditional teaching method.

Table 1. Pretest and posttest performance of the control group

Test	n	Mean	SD	Mean gain	t
Pretest	33	6.02	1.23	171%	-47.9651*
Posttest	33	16.33	1.60		

2. Students' Performance in the Experimental Group. To determine the effects of collaborative learning on the student's performance in Probability, the t -test for independent samples was employed. The results revealed that the posttest mean score of the students taught using collaborative learning was 18.98 (SD = 1.04) which is much higher than the pretest mean score of 5.77 (SD = 1.02). The t -test value of -57.1309 is significant at $p < 0.05$, thus, collaborative learning positively affects the students' performance in Probability.

Table 2. Pretest and posttest performance of the experimental group

Test	n	Mean	SD	Mean gain	t
Pretest	33	5.77	1.02	229%	57.1309*
Posttest	33	18.98	1.04		

3. Comparison of the Students' Performances in Pretest. In comparing the performance of the participants during the pretest, students in the control group have a mean score of 6.02 (SD = 1.23) which is a bit greater than the mean score of those in the experimental group with 5.77 (SD = 1.02). However, the t -test result of $t(32) = 1.1214$, $p > 0.05$ denotes that there is no significant difference between the pretest scores. The result reveals that the prior knowledge of the two groups of participants is of the same level.

Table 3. Comparison of the pretest scores of the control and experimental groups

Test	n	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t
Control	33	6.02	1.23	4%	1.1214
Experimental	33	5.77	1.02		

4. Comparison of the Students' Performances in Posttest. After employing the t -test for independent samples, the mean score in the posttest of the students taught using collaborative learning showed greater performance than those taught using the traditional method. This was evidenced by the mean score of 18.98 (SD = 1.04) for the experimental group and 16.33 (SD = 1.60) for the control group. Further, the $t(32) = -12.1940$, $p < 0.05$, depicts that a significant difference between the post-test performance in the Probability of the two groups of respondents exists. On this note, the students taught in collaborative

learning performed better than those taught using the traditional teaching method. Thus, collaborative learning is more effective in teaching Probability.

Table 4. Comparison of the post-test performance of the control and experimental groups

Test	n	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t
Control	33	16.33	1.60	16%	-12.1940*
Experimental	33	18.98	1.04		

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study revealed that collaborative learning has a significant effect on the student's performance in Probability. The experimental group shows significant improvement in their posttest scores compared to that of the control group. The result suggests that the increase in the student's performance was attributed to the significant effect of collaborative learning. The findings of this study, therefore, are consistent with the results reported by Curtis (2009), Hossain (2013), Chin (2010), Melihan et al, (2011), and Zakaria (2013). Further, the study also compared the students' performance under traditional teaching and collaborative learning which found that students taught using collaborative learning performed better than those taught using the traditional method. These findings were congruent with that of Arney (2010) because students who were exposed to more types of approaches tend to truly learn math. Working together in small groups will help them achieve the common goal (Curtis, 2009) through effective classroom management (Norton, 2009).

After the conduct of the study, the students under collaborative learning understand the concepts of Probability and their applications to various disciplines better than those under traditional teaching methods. Because of working with peers, they were able to gain self-confidence (Zakaria et al, 2013) and improve their social aspect. They too also appreciate the applications and importance of probability in their daily lives.

Conclusions

A significant difference between the pretest and posttest was determined through the statistical treatment applied. This shows that the participants gained knowledge after the teaching and learning process. No significant difference, however, was found in terms of the pretest scores between the two groups of respondents which implies that they both have the same level of prior knowledge. On the other hand, a significant difference exists between the post-test scores of those under control and experimental groups. After the treatment, it was found out that the students taught using collaborative learning performed better in Probability than those taught using traditional teaching methods. The result implies that collaborative learning is effective in teaching Probability. The students under

collaborative learning also increased their interest in Probability-related problems and they were able to develop their social relationship with each other. They become more responsible for their learning as well as the learning of their peers.

Recommendations

Collaborative learning should be employed by the teachers in teaching mathematics to develop the student's interest and confidence in learning math. A triad or small group of four is ideal to lessen the possibility of arising conflicts of ideas. Further, it will be easier to monitor the progress of each member if the group size is small. Students with a common interest or living closely with each other should be grouped so that activities outside the school may easily be conducted. Profiling of learning styles and multiple intelligences may also be done so that the teacher may suit the activities based on the interests, intelligence, and learning styles of the students. Finally, the study may be replicated by applying collaborative learning to other subjects or branches of mathematics.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before the distribution of the instrument, a letter of permission to conduct the study was submitted to the Director for Research. After it had been approved, another letter was presented to the Director for Instruction and the Campus Administrator for the approval of the conduct of the experimental study. When permission was granted, consent forms were given to the Director of Student Welfare Services, the Guidance Counselor of the university, and the participants. The said consent forms include the purpose of the study, the assurance of confidentiality, and the right of the participant to withdraw anytime they feel uncomfortable. The respondents were also informed of the possible presentation and publication of the study.

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